

Jestbooks and Drinking Songs William Byrd and Popular Culture

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In John Hilton's *Catch that Catch Can* printed by John Playford in 1652, an unexpected name appears next to the drinking song 'Come Drink to Me / I Have Loved the Jolly Tankard': 'Mr William Bird.'¹ Byrd's name was spuriously attached to many catches in the mid- to late-eighteenth century, including most famously, *Non nobis Domine*;² however this appearance in Playford's collection was less than 30-years after Byrd's death. Nor was it a Latin canon or a country catch (like the equally spurious 'Hey Ho! to the Greenwood'), but rather a drinking song.

Hilton's *Catch that Catch Can* was not the first appearance of 'Come Drink to Me / I Have Loved the Jolly Tankard', which had been previously printed anonymously by Thomas Ravenscroft in 1609 and a year earlier by John Playford in 1651.³ All Ravenscroft's rounds and catches had been printed without attribution. However, the majority of Latin canons in Ravenscroft's print have now been identified as from a continental theory treatise, and it is by no means impossible that some others were by well-known composers of the day.⁴ At this point in its history, the catch was not a genre to associate one's name with (even Ravenscroft kept his identity hidden in his earliest publications).

'Come Drink to Me / I Have Loved the Jolly Tankard' is at the more complex end of the catch spectrum. The catch is built on a scalar hexachordal ground (sung to 'Come Drink to Me'), around which lengthy phrases are woven and out of which

finally emerges a faster, triple time melody that seems likely to be a popular drinking song of the day. Nevertheless, the catch has been rejected from the Byrd canon and was criticised by Philip Brett for being 'rhythmically square' and 'harmonically awkward' with its parallel octaves.⁵

In the 1652 publication, Byrd's name is only given in the table of contents but is not printed next to the notated song. This is unusual, as the reverse is usually true in this collection.⁶ This oddity perhaps suggests that the name was initially a last-minute addition in 1652 and that either Playford or Hilton became aware of the attribution late in the production process. Yet the appearance of Byrd's name against this catch is also not a one-off; rather it was continuously associated with Byrd in Playford's catchbooks. Indeed, in all subsequent editions Byrd's name follows the norm and appears above the notated song rather than in the contents, thereby becoming even more closely associated with the song as singers would have seen it if performing the catch from notation.⁷ It is highly likely, therefore, that seventeenth-century catch singers would have believed 'Come Drink to Me / I Have Loved the Jolly Tankard' to be by William Byrd.

My aim here, though, is not to resituate this catch in the Byrd canon. Attributions in catchbooks are often unreliable (though it is worth noting that this occurrence is not symptomatic of any wider trend of associating older anonymous catches to Byrd or

¹ John Hilton, ed, *Catch that Catch Can, or A Choice Collection of Catches, Rounds and Canons for 3 or 4 Voyces* (London, 1652), Table of Contents and 70.

² See Philip Brett, 'Did Byrd Write "Non Nobis, Domine"?' *The Musical Times*, 113 (1972), 855–7; more recently on possible attributions for *Non nobis Domine* see David Humphreys, 'Wilder's Hand?', *The Musical Times*, 144 (2003), 4. Byrd's earliest biographers did accept these pieces in the Byrd canon, as in Edmund Fellowes, *William Byrd*, 2nd edn (London: Oxford University Press, 1948), 173–82.

³ Thomas Ravenscroft, *Pammelia, Musicks Miscellanie, or Mixed Varietie of Pleasant Roundelays, and Delightfull Catches of 3.4.5.6.7.8.9.10. Parts in One* (London, 1609), p.31 (No. 68); John Playford, ed., *Musick and Mirth, Presented in a Choice Collection of Rounds or Catches for Three Voyces* (London, 1651), 5.

⁴ John Milsom, 'About a Round', *Music of the Josquin Era* (forthcoming).

⁵ Brett, 'Did Byrd Write "Non Nobis, Domine"?' 856.

⁶ Aside from the numerous *Gloria Patri* settings that are distinguished by their composer, the only secular song whose composer is named in the table of contents is *Now that the Spring* by John Hilton himself, which also appears without attribution on p.1 of the collection.

⁷ In the John Hilton and John Playford, ed., *Catch that Catch Can, or A Choice Collection of Catches, Rounds and Canons: Being Three or Four Parts in One* (London, 1658), 66; *Catch that Catch Can Or A New Collection of Catches, Rounds and Canons: Being Three or Four Parts in One* (London, 1663), 66; John Playford, ed., *Catch that Catch Can or The Musical Companion* (London, 1667), 26; and in John Playford, ed., *The Musical Companion in Two Books The First Containing Catches and Rounds for Three Voyces* (London, 1672/3), 20.

other composers of his generation in Playford's collections). I am more interested in the fact that it was presumably plausible for seventeenth-century musicians—including a Cambridge-trained and London-based church musician such as John Hilton—to associate a drinking song catch with Byrd. This offers a quite different perspective on Byrd's image in the immediate generation that succeeded him and gives us pause to reconsider the nuances of his posthumous reputation, especially as it might have been viewed by those more removed from the composer's immediate circle and shaped by those more ubiquitous genres that traversed orality and print.

When discussing Byrd's reputation among his contemporaries or immediately succeeding generations, the sources that have tended to be cited by scholars are those that emphasise Byrd's high esteem and serious nature. For example, colleagues in the Chapel Royal such as Thomas Morley described Byrd as 'neuer without reuerence to be named of the musicians', while in his commonplace book John Baldwin labelled him, 'famus man of skill: and iudgement greate profounde'.⁸ In a popular conduct book of the day for gentlemen, Henry Peacham described Byrd as 'being of himselfe naturally disposed to Grauitie and Pietie, his veine is not so much for light Madrigals or Canzonets'.⁹ This image of the serious Byrd who troubled himself little with 'light' or 'foreign' genres such as the madrigal has endured in Byrd scholarship.¹⁰ Byrd's first biographer, Edmund Fellowes took his lead from Peacham, stating that 'rightly recognised that... this special excellence was due to his natural disposition to "Gravitie and Pietie"'.¹¹ Elsewhere, Fellowes

described Byrd as a man who 'commanded affection and respect. And he was a man of deep and sincere religious conviction'.¹² While more recent biographers tend to be more cautious in offering such explicit character judgements, such an image of Byrd is still current in the *Grove Music* article begun by Joseph Kerman and updated by Kerry McCarthy when it states: 'Decorum, solidity and a certain reticence of expression were qualities that were prized in his formative years, qualities that came to him naturally'.¹³ Indeed, the *Grove Music* article does not even mention the catches and canons in the list of spurious works, so keen is current scholarship to dissociate such frivolities from Byrd.

However, these lofty, laudatory statements by gentlemen and prominent colleagues were not the only sources through which Byrd's reputation was formed and disseminated. As Mike Smith has noted, several of Byrd songs and instrumental variations seem to reveal a liking for bawdy ballad tunes and lyrics that indicates a neglected lighter side to Byrd's creativity and character.¹⁴ Moreover Byrd makes several appearances in one of the most widespread and popular genres of print during his lifetime: the jestbook. Jestbooks were collections of merry tales, jokes, and witty repartees designed to produce laughter. Although the culture of jesting was oral in nature, jestbooks could take a wide variety of forms including individual detached jests, short comic stories, or longer pseudo-biographical narratives of the escapades of a central character.¹⁵ Almost all jestbooks were anonymous, but many associated themselves with real but now-dead comic figures such as John Scoggin and Richard Tarlton, or else with figures of popular legend such

⁸ Thomas Morley, *A Plaine and Easie Introduction to Practicall Musicke* (London, 1597), 115; British Library, R.M.24.d.2 'Baldwin Commonplace Book', final pages.

⁹ Henry Peacham, *The Compleat Gentleman Fashioning him Absolute in the Most Necessary & Commendable Qualities Concerning Minde or Bodie that may be Required in a Noble Gentleman* (London, 1622), 100.

¹⁰ On the notion of 'light' music in early modern times and in contemporary scholarship see Katie Bank, *Knowledge Building in Early Modern English Music* (Abingdon, 2021), chap. 1.

¹¹ Fellowes, *William Byrd*, 241.

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ Joseph Kerman and Kerry McCarthy, 'Byrd, William', *Grove Music Online* (2001) <<https://doi.org/10.1093/gmo/9781561592630.article.04487>>.

¹⁴ Mike Smith, 'Bawdry, Balladry, Byrd', *Annual Byrd Newsletter* 10 (2004), 16–19. Smith also notes previous passing comments on Byrd's engagement with such themes by John Milsom, Oliver Neighbour and Laurence Dreyfus.

¹⁵ This tripartite definition of types of jestbooks originates in E. Schulz, *Die englischen Schwankbücher bis herab zu Dobson's Drie Bobs, Palaestra* 117 (Berlin, 1912), but still informs modern critical approaches to the genre: Ian Munro and Anne Lake Prescott, 'Jest Books' *The Oxford Handbook of English Prose 1500-1640*, ed. Andrew Hadfield, (Oxford, 2013), 343–59 (at 344); F. P. Wilson, 'The English Jestbooks of the Sixteenth and Early Seventeenth Centuries', *Huntington Library Quarterly* 2 (1939), 121–58 (at 122).

as George a Green, Long Meg, and Oliver Smug.¹⁶ Within these books, the same jests were often recycled and retold from collection to collection.¹⁷ The chapbook format of many jestbooks give them the appearance of popular literature: cheaply printed, small pamphlets in blackletter type, set in common, everyday contexts and addressing coarse topics.¹⁸ However, jests had classical pedigree having been praised by ancient authors such as Cicero and Quintilian, and humanistic discourse promoted the revival of classical wit and the benefits of jesting for health, conviviality, rhetoric, and political ambition.¹⁹ Indeed jestbooks often anticipated a broad and multifarious audience. *The Booke of Bulls* (1636) has prefaces ‘to the blinde reader’, and ‘to the discerning reader’ while John Taylor’s *Wit and Mirth* (1628) describes its content as originating in taverns, alehouses, tobacco shops, highways, water-passages, but ‘apothegmatically bundled vp’, referring to the verse tags that he adds to draw out their potential moral message or meaning.²⁰ Jestbooks evoked the broad spectrum of potential readers, contexts, and responses to their contents.

Byrd makes two jestbook appearances: the first in *Dobsons Drie Bobbes Sonne and Heire to Skoggin* (London, 1607) and the second in *Tarltons Iests Drawne into these Three Parts* (London, 1613, but circulating at least in partial form by 1590s).²¹ I will also briefly discuss a possible third jestbook appearance that has been connected with Byrd in *The Booke of Bulls, Baited with Two Centuries of Bold Jestes* (London, 1636), though in this case I will argue that the ‘Byrd’ in question is not the composer. This article will review Byrd’s jestbook appearances and

their potential impact on Byrd’s image in the eyes of his near contemporaries, reflecting on how this might lead us to adjust aspects of our own view of the composer today.

Although the date at which the third part of *Tarltons Iests* initially appeared is uncertain, ‘Tarlton’s Wit between a Bird and a Woodcocke’ is likely to have been Byrd’s most well-known jestbook appearance.²² Richard Tarleton was a comic actor in the Queen’s Men and the Queen’s favourite jester.²³ After his death in 1588, Tarleton’s name was attached to several jestbooks including *Tarltons Iests*.²⁴ This book is a loose collection of jests unified only by association with the hero Tarleton and grouped into three categories: court, city, and country. As was common for the genre, many of *Tarltons Iests* recycle older, traditional jests;²⁵ however, the jest in which William Byrd appears seems to be new as it depends specifically on his name and that of the lesser-known Tudor composer, Clement Woodcock.

The Byrd-related jest opens ‘*Tarltons prettie Countrie Iests*’, by which is meant jests that take place out of London, rather than necessarily in a rural location. The Byrd jest is short enough to cite in full:

In the City of Gloucester, Master Bird of the Chappell met with Tarlton, who joyfull to regreet other, went to visit his friends: amongst the rest, M. Bird of the Queens Chappell visited Master Woodcock of the Colledge, where méeting, many friendly speeches past, amongst which, M. Woodcocke challenged M. Bird of kin:

¹⁶ Munro and Prescott, ‘Jest Books’, 352–7; Wilson, ‘English Jestbooks’, 133–8; Adam Smyth, ‘“Divines into Dry Vines”: Forms of Jestings in Renaissance England’, in *Formal Matters: Reading the Materials of English Renaissance Literature*, ed. A. K. Eutermann and A. Kisey (Manchester, 2013), 55–76 (at 59–60).

¹⁷ Wilson, ‘English Jestbooks’, 126; Smyth, ‘Divines into Dry Vines’, 59; Tim Somers, ‘Jesting Culture and Religious Politics in Seventeenth-Century England’, *Historical Research*, 95 (2022), 19–44 (21–22).

¹⁸ Munro and Prescott, ‘Jest Books’, 354; Somers, ‘Jesting Culture’, 20–21; Smyth, ‘Divines into Dry Vines’, 65.

¹⁹ Munro and Prescott, ‘Jest Books’, 345–51; Smyth, ‘Divines into Dry Vines’, 63–5.

²⁰ John Taylor, *Wit and Mirth Chargeably Collected out of Tauernes, Ordinaries, Innes, Bowling Greenes, and Allyes, Alehouses, Tobacco Shops, Highwaies, and Water-Passages: Made Vp, and Fashioned into Clinches, Bulls, Quirkes, Yerkes, Quips, and Ierkes: Apothegmatically Bundled Vp and Garbled at the Request of Old Iohn Garrets Ghost* (London, 1628); A.S. Gent, *The Booke of Bulls Baited with Two Centuries of Bold Jestes, and Nimble-Lies, Or a Combat betweene Sense and Non-sense, being at Strike who Shall Infuse Most Myrth into the Gentle-Reader* (London, 1636), prefatory materials.

²¹ The second part of *Tarltons Iests* was registered in 1600: <<https://stationersregister.online/entry/SRO4330>>. In 1609, *Tarltons Iests* were reassigned to John Budge: <<https://stationersregister.online/entry/SRO5572>>.

²² *Tarltons Iests Drawne into These Three Parts* (London, 1613), sig.[C4]r.

²³ For more detail see Katherine Duncan-Jones, ‘The Life, Death and Afterlife of Richard Tarlton’, *The Review of English Studies* New. Ser 65 (2014), 18–32.

²⁴ Munro and Prescott, ‘Jest Books’, 356–7.

²⁵ P. M. Zall, *A Nest of Ninnies and Other English Jestbooks of the Seventeenth Century* (Lincoln, NE, 1970), 91.

who mused that he was of his affinity and he never knew it: yes says M. Woodcocke, every Woodcocke is a Bird, therefore it must needs be so. Lord, Sir, says Tarlton, you are wide, for though every Woodcocke be a Bird, yet every Bird is not a Woodcocke. So M. Woodcocke like a Woodcocke bit his lip, and mum bugged was silent.²⁶

Despite the verisimilitude given by details of the people and places, this jest should not be read literally as an anecdotal account of an actual meeting. Nevertheless, the people and places would presumably have been plausible to contemporary readers. Gloucester might seem an odd place to situate Byrd, but the city was only a few miles from the manor of Longney, which he was granted by the Queen in 1577, and which was one of the subjects of his many legal issues.²⁷ Clement Woodcock (c.1540–90) was a contemporary of Byrd's with five surviving consort pieces (including two In Nomines and two arrangements of popular tunes). He was a Lay Clerk at King's College, a singer at Canterbury Cathedral until 1570, and then Organist and Master of the Choristers at Chichester Cathedral, but has no known connection to Gloucester.²⁸

There are two key elements to the jest. The first is a pun on the composers' ornithological names. The woodcock is a woodland wading bird, which was known in Tudor times for being dull and particularly easy to snare. As such, 'woodcock' was also a name often applied to a gullible or foolish person, a characterisation that the composer lives up to in this jest.²⁹ The second element to the jest is that of an attempt at wit that backfires on the instigator to the amusement of others. Tarlton's rejoinder plays on the relative status of the composers, and the presumptuousness of Woodcock in claiming affinity with a musician of Byrd's status. The clear message is that Byrd is a different class of musician, and Woodcock is a fool to be so unaware of his place in the pecking order.

The jest both expects the audience to know who Byrd is and further enhances Byrd's status through his endorsement by such a famous and popular figure as Tarleton. Admiration for Tarleton spanned the spectrum of Tudor society from the Queen and court to the London theatregoer. Tarleton's endorsement was all the more realistic as his regular appearances at court meant that he would likely have known of Byrd's status as a favoured musician of the Queen (indeed he may even have met Byrd on one of these court occasions). *Tarltons Iests* was a chapbook of only 24 folios printed in blackletter type, the same as used for broadside ballads and the first script one would be taught to read.³⁰ Such jestbooks were designed to appeal and be accessible to a broad readership, so the effect of this jest would have been to similarly popularise Byrd's status beyond the courtly and aristocratic audiences who purchased his music publications or had ready access to hearing his music performed. Moreover, with repeated editions in 1620, 1630, and 1638, *Tarltons Iests* continued to shape Byrd's posthumous identity too.

Byrd's other jestbook appearance came in *Dobsons Drie Bobbes* (1607). This book was a jest biofiction that told the story of the life of George Dobson, a choirboy at Durham Cathedral School, and later scholar at Christ's College, Cambridge. At the start of the story Dobson is adopted by his uncle. Initially mocked and bullied by his classmates for his country manner, Dobson eventually decides to turn troublemaker and get his revenge. 'Dry bobs' are pranks and escapades, and those Dobson plays on his classmates include locking them in cupboards, stealing from them, and tricking them into sitting on hot stones that burn through the seat of their trousers.

Dobsons Drie Bobbes has such a high degree of verisimilitude in the places, customs, legal/financial technicalities, and detailed descriptions of material objects which it contains that it has been regarded

²⁶ *Tarltons Iests*, sig.[C4]r.

²⁷ John Harley, *The World of William Byrd: Musicians, Merchants and Magnates* (Burlington, VT, 2010), 219.

²⁸ Warwick Edwards, 'Woodcock, Clement', *Grove Music Online* (2001) <<https://doi.org/10.1093/gmo/9781561592630.article.30547>>.

²⁹ *Oxford English Dictionary*, 'woodcock (n.)' (2023) <<https://doi.org/10.1093/OED/8470115952>>.

³⁰ Keith Thomas, 'The Meaning of Literacy in Early Modern England,' in *The Written Word: Literacy in Transition*, ed. Gerd Baumann (Oxford, 1986), 97–131 (at 99).

by literary scholars as a work of historical fiction.³¹ Although published in 1607 and assumed to be written around the same time, the characters are identifiable figures who were living and working in Durham during the 1560s, including the protagonist George Dobson (a known choirboy), his uncle Sir Thomas Pentley (a canon at the cathedral), fellow chorister Raikebaines, and John Bromley, master of the choir school and organist. Moreover, the places featured are similarly realistic, including the local churches and layout of Durham cathedral precinct, and the text is full of specific details about customs, rituals, objects, and legal, financial, or ecclesiastical technicalities.³²

The reference to Byrd is another of these realistic details which appears in Dobson's last school prank: 'How Dobson devised a holiday and endangered his fellows a whipping'.³³ The somewhat convoluted escapade takes place around Midsummer. The choristers have finished morning prayers at the cathedral and are on their way to school. Dobson uses the chance closure of the Tailor's shop to convince his peers that there is in fact no school because it is a feast day and a holiday. Dobson encourages them to go instead to the Moorhouse (presumably an alehouse or tavern) where he tells them that he has laid on breakfast and a shooting match.³⁴ Dobson promises to go to the schoolhouse to get permission from the schoolmaster for them to observe the holiday.

Dobson does go to the schoolhouse; however, when the schoolmaster, Master Bromeley, arrives, Dobson plays the innocent and claims that his classmates are the ones suggesting the holiday and that he dared not go with them to shoot because he could not think what holiday it could be, and nor could he persuade his peers to wait until Master Bromeley arrived. Bromeley checks that there is no

holiday and then sends Dobson to command his peers to come back to school. Dobson therefore returns to his peers but spins them the story that 'diuers Gentlemen of good sort' have arrived from London on their way to Berwick.³⁵ The gentlemen, he claims, have sought out Master Bromeley wanting to see the school and its scholars, and so the Master has sent Dobson to ask them to come to school, despite it being a holiday.

Crucially for our interest in the story, Dobson states that the gentlemen from London have requested a song 'and haue brought themselues diuersitie of descant, lately set forth by Maister *Bird Doctor of our Arte*'.³⁶ Believing Dobson's tale, the pupils head back to the school hoping to be rewarded by the gentlemen for their singing. As they near the school, his classmates get cold feet seeing Master Bromeley standing alone, but Dobson assures them that the London gentlemen have just gone to see the 'Chancellour shrine of S. *Cuthbert*'.³⁷

At this point things do not seem to go quite to plan for Dobson. After the pupils arrive, Master Bromeley bolts the door and enquires as to why they had neglected to come to school and had not followed Dobson's example incoming to see him first, whereupon the scholars explain what Dobson has done. Fearing a beating Dobson 'skipped into an old Jake [toilets]... protesting that forth of that place he would not come unless his master would solemnly swear to remit and forgive unto him all offences past', and threatening that, should any harm come to him while down there, he would ensure that the Master was blamed.³⁸ Worried that Dobson has gone mad in his desperation (and also more than a little gullible, it appears), Master Bromeley swears that he will pardon Dobson and a rope is cast down to bring the schoolboy up.

³¹ Alex David, *Renaissance Historical Fiction: Sidney, Deloney, Nashe* (Woodbridge, 2011), 89–99 (e.g. 93); on *Dobsons Drie Bobbes* and the development of the novel see also, Avril S. O'Brien, 'Dobsons Drie Bobbes: A Significant Contribution to the Development of Prose Fiction', *Studies in English Literature, 1500-1900*, 12 (1972), 55-70.

³² David, *Renaissance Historical Fiction*, 92–3; O'Brien, 'Dobsons Drie Bobbes,' 68–9; E.A. Horsman, ed., *Dobson's Drie Bobbes: A Story of Sixteenth-Century Durham* (Oxford, 1955), ix–xvi.

³³ *Dobsons Drie Bobbes Sonne and Heire to Skoggin* (London, 1607), sigs [L4]v–M3r.

³⁴ Elvet Moor House still exists just off the Great North Road about half a mile south of where it meets the road from Durham to Crook: Horsman, ed., *Dobson's Drie Bobbes*, xii.

³⁵ *Dobsons Drie Bobbes*, sig. M2r.

³⁶ *Ibid.*, sig. M2v.

³⁷ *Ibid.*

³⁸ *Ibid.*, sig. M3r.

Byrd's name appears in the jest as a specific detail designed to make Dobson's lies more plausible to his schoolmates. Perhaps too, the name of Byrd and the promise of new music is intended to entice them back, eager to sing the latest works from London's most famous composer. Byrd was not in fact a doctor, but Dobson presumably adds this detail to inflate Byrd's reputation further still. The episode suggests that Byrd's was a name to conjure with, even in a part of the kingdom as remote as Durham.

Like Dobson's classmates, the reader is surely expected to know who Byrd is in order to understand the practical joke that Dobson is playing and how wittily he is deceiving his fellows. However, a knowledgeable reader may have understood further layers to this story if they were aware of Byrd's position as a practising Catholic serving in Elizabeth's Protestant Chapel Royal. As literary scholar Alex David has noted, the post-Reformation disruption at Durham Cathedral is pointedly absent from the world of *Dobsons Drie Bobbes*, despite its 1560s setting.³⁹ James Pilkington was appointed bishop of Durham in 1561 (the period in which Dobson exploits are set). He ordered the bells of the collegiate church of St Andrew Auckland to be smashed and removed officials to replace them with more ardent reformers. His wife supposedly burned the banner of local saint, St Cuthbert. Such was the local disquiet regarding these reforms that one of the major acts of the Northern Rebellion of 1579 was to occupy Durham Cathedral and to restore altars and images in local churches.⁴⁰ David reads the absence of this religious turbulence from *Dobsons Drie Bobbes* as creating 'a myth of an Elizabethan "Merrie England"', free from religious controversy and emphasising continuity and tradition.⁴¹ David even suggests that reference to Byrd's music was intended to be indicative of that harmony within the cathedral.⁴²

However, given Byrd's Catholicism, the reference to the composer and his music is not a straightforward marker of social or religious harmony. Indeed, the evocation of Byrd is one of a number of Catholic undercurrents in this particular jest. In suggesting that the gentlemen from London are visiting St Cuthbert's shrine, Dobson equates them with pilgrims; the gentlemen are religious conservatives, if not Catholics. Moreover, Dobson's whole jest depends on the traditionally Catholic notion that there is a saint's day to justify the holiday and even Master Bromeley acknowledges the possibility that there might be such a day 'either by the prescript of the Church or the general custom of the Country' and has to check the day and time of year to ensure that this is not the case.⁴³ In this context, the fact that the gentlemen have brought Byrd's music specifically may not be solely related to his pre-eminent status as royal composer, but also to Byrd's position straddling religious divides: serving in the royal household of a Protestant Queen but equally embedded in England's traditional Catholic past through attending clandestine services and composing music for the Catholic liturgy.⁴⁴ Indeed Dobson's suggestion is never that Byrd's music will be sung in the cathedral, but rather just by the boys at the school, perhaps registering a tension between permitted liturgical practice and local sympathies. Either way, Byrd is represented as a foremost London composer whose reputation has spread to the furthest reaches of England, and who despite serving at the royal court, can be readily understood to be associated with traditional Catholicism in the form of saints' days and shrines.

Finally, I will briefly explore one slightly later jest which on first reading also appears to relate to William Byrd and a fellow musician, but in fact turns out not to do so. This jest appears in *The Booke of Bulls* (1636). Again, this jest is short enough to quote in full:

A Captaine in the *Low-Countreys* being in the company of one, who was a very

³⁹ David, *Renaissance Historical Fiction*, 93–4.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, 94–5.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, 97.

⁴² *Ibid.*, 98.

⁴³ *Dobsons Drie Bobbes*, sig. M2r.

⁴⁴ See for example, Kerry McCarthy, *Byrd* (Oxford, 2013), chaps. 5, 11, and 13.

goodly and a properman demanded his name, and learning that he was named *Bird*; hee said, this is not that *Bird* whom *Taverner* kil'd, is it?⁴⁵

This example is symptomatic of a brief fashion for a particular type of jest c.1636–38: the bull. Bulls were verbal slips—involuntary or deliberate—that result in nonsensical or paradoxical statements. Bulls could be either intentionally funny or unintentional signs of foolishness or lack of understanding.⁴⁶

While the text here is not so explicit that ‘Bird’ is the composer of that name, the combination of two names associated with musicians—Byrd and Taverner—conjures up associations with musicians in the mid-seventeenth century. While the composer John Taverner had died over 90 years ago, he was still being cited in published lists of English masters of music, as in *Wits Common Wealth* (1634).⁴⁷ Equally, in 1636, the name Taverner might also have brought to mind the John Taverner who was currently serving as Professor for Music Gresham College, a post he had held since 1610, delivering free lectures on music to a diverse audience of merchants and citizens in London.⁴⁸

The bull element of the anecdote, however, does not rely on any association with music. Rather, the nonsensical element lies in asking the living person you are being introduced to whether they are the same person as one you know to have been killed. The names of Byrd and Taverner are not part of the humour here as they were in the Byrd/Woodcock jest. There does not seem to be any particular pun around the name of Taverner—someone who keeps a tavern—and birds.

Moreover, while the cause of Byrd’s death in 1623 is unknown, he certainly was not killed by John Taverner the composer (who died in 1545), and there is no reason to think he was killed by the Gresham Lecturer either.

There was, however, a legal case in 1614 in which a Richard Taverner was tried for the murder of one John Bird. In 1609, Bird had challenged Taverner to a duel of swords over an unpaid debt. The duel took place in Theobalds Park during which Taverner killed Bird. Taverner initially fled to the continent but returned to England in 1615 and was subsequently tried for murder in 1616. The incident was recorded in the State Papers because it was included in the news that Londoner John Chamberlain conveyed to Dudley Carleton in February 1609 and the case was still being cited in the nineteenth century as establishing that it was murder if the challenged party killed their rival in a dual.⁴⁹ The protagonists of this newsworthy incident seem a more likely Bird and Taverner to be known to a captain in the Netherlands than the musicians of these names, and make more sense of the bull’s reference to killing. While the incident occurs several decades before *The Booke of Bulls* was published, this is true of some of the few other bulls in which names individuals occur, including one naming John Bull as Gresham Lecturer of Music, a post he had not held since 1607.⁵⁰ William Byrd is almost certainly not the ‘Bird’ referred to in this particular jest.

Yet what are we to make of Byrd’s two earlier jestbook appearances and how might they help us to make sense of a seventeenth-century mindset that could comfortably attribute a drinking catch to the composer? What links Byrd’s catchbook appearance with the two jestbook cameos in

⁴⁵ A.S. Gent, *Booke of Bulls*, 20–21.

⁴⁶ Lucy Munro, ‘Richard Brome and *The Booke of Bulls*: Situating *The New Academy*, or *The New Exchange*’, *The Ben Jonson Journal*, 13 (2006), 125–38, at pp. 128–9.

⁴⁷ Francis Meres, *Wits Common Wealth: The Second Part* (London, 1634), 639; copying directing from Frances Meres, *Palladis Tamia: Wits Treasury* (London, 1598), f. 288v.

⁴⁸ See, John Taverner, *On the Origin and Progress of the Art of Music*, ed. Joseph Ortiz, *Music Theory in Britain, 1500–1700: Critical Editions* (New York, 2018).

⁴⁹ John Chamberlain, ‘Chamberlain to Carleton. April 30, 1616. MS SP 14/86 f.281’, Records Assembled by the State Paper Office. The National Archives (Kew, United Kingdom) *State Papers Online* <<https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/MC4323684189/SPOL?u=unn&sid=bookmark-SPOL&xid=9402ec30>>; John Chamberlain, ‘Chamberlain to Carleton. April 30, 1616. MS SP 14/86 f.281’, Records Assembled by the State Paper Office. The National Archives (Kew, United Kingdom), *State Papers Online* <<https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/MC4323684189/SPOL?u=unn&sid=bookmark-SPOL&xid=9402ec30>>; William Snyder, *Great Opinions by Great Judges: A Collection of Important Judicial Opinions by Eminent Judges* (New York, 1883), 11–14. See also Lloyd Bowen, *Anatomy of a Duel in Jacobean England: Gentry Honour, Violence and the Law* (Woodbridge, 2021), 192–3.

⁵⁰ A.S. Gent, *Booke of Bulls*, 84.

Dobsons Drie Bobbes and *Tarltons Iests* is that these publications both place Byrd in a more playful and humorous context than other sources and spread his reputation further through society than most of his music publications would have reached. While *Dobsons Drie Bobbes* was somewhat longer than *Tarltons Iests* (56 folios compared to 24), it was nevertheless still relatively short and printed in the same blackletter type that ensured the widest possible readability. Playford's catchbooks also envisaged a wide audience. Catches represented the simplest form of part-singing and while sightreading from the books would require musical literacy, taking part in the singing did not as such short songs could be readily learnt by ear. Hilton and Playford's catchbooks were regularly reprinted and expanded over the seventeenth century, each time reproducing Byrd's name in association with 'I Have a Jolly Tankard'.⁵¹ Indeed both jests and catches enjoyed considerable breadth of audience, crossing boundaries of class, blurring distinctions between learned and popular entertainment, and traversing written versus oral dissemination. It seems likely that portrayals of Byrd in media such as these had wider reaching impact on perceptions of the composer than those found in manuscript inscriptions, theory treatises, conduct literature, or the prefaces of music prints.

Moreover, these appearances of Byrd in the context of popular forms of entertainment are an indication of the pervasiveness of his reputation and the familiarity of his name beyond the courtly and elite circles who may have had direct contact with the composer and his music. The image of Byrd that was being projected in the popular imagination upheld his status as a preeminent composer of his day—and indeed relied on this—but for those who met Byrd in the pages of jestbooks or as the author of a drinking catch he is less likely to have appeared as the composer 'naturally disposed to gravity' described by Peacham or the staid and pious composer often

represented in most modern scholarship. Indeed, in the seventeenth century, as drinking culture became increasingly associated with royalist, anti-puritan sentiments,⁵² Byrd's association with drinking catches may have seemed all the more plausible, in a nostalgic or conservative way that is perhaps not so dissimilar to Dobson's use of Byrd to nod to conservative religious custom.

The 'real' person of Byrd is as lost to us as it was to most of the jestbook audiences and Playford's catch singers. Yet Byrd's appearance in such mirthful contexts should give us pause to reconsider the potential significance of some of Byrd's more light-hearted compositions in his sixteenth and seventeenth-century reception. Pastoral partsongs such as 'Though Amaryllis Dance in Green', 'Who made thee Hob Forsake the Plough?', and 'Come Jolly Swains', and even Byrd's early contributions to the English madrigal—the two versions of 'This Sweet and Merry Month of May' and 'The Fair Young Virgin', the latter also published with the Italian text, 'La virginella'—have still received relatively little critical attention,⁵³ which is likely to be at least in part due to the difficulty of reconciling them within our received image of Byrd. However, such pieces may not have seemed so peripheral to his reputation for those who had encountered Byrd's name in the context of jests and catches. Afterall, Byrd always claimed in his song publications to provide music for all humours, including the 'merrie' and those 'of myrth'.⁵⁴

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⁵¹ See above note 4.

⁵² On which see Stacey Jocoy, 'The Role of the Catch in England's Civil Wars', *Essays on Music and Culture in Honor of Herbert Kellman*, ed., Barbara Hagg (Paris, 2001) 325–34.

⁵³ A recent exception is Jeremy L. Smith's discussion of the pastoral songs in *Verse and Voice in Byrd's Song Collections of 1588 and 1589* (Woodbridge, 2016), though he aims to show their potential political readings and literary qualities, rather than embracing a lighter vein in Byrd's output.

⁵⁴ William Byrd, *Psalmes, Sonets & Songs of Sadnes and Pietie* (London, 1588), 'The Epistle to the Reader'; *Songs of Sundrie Natures Some of Grauitie, and Others of Myrth* (London, 1589), title page; *Psalmes, Songs, and Sonnets* (London, 1611), 'To all true louers of Musicke'.